

ENHANCING LITERATURE TEACHING THROUGH SUGGESTOPEDIA: A PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

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Enhancing Literature Teaching through Suggestopedia: A Pedagogical Approach

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the effectiveness of suggestopedia in teaching literature to Grade 11 students at Zapatera National High School, Cebu City, during the 2022-2023 academic year. Using a quasi-experimental design with 60 students divided into control and experimental groups, the study compares pretest and posttest performances. The experimental group received instruction through suggestopedia, while the control group followed traditional lecture-based methods. Both groups showed improvement in posttest scores, but the experimental group achieved significantly higher results. These findings suggest that suggestopedia enhances literature instruction, making learning more enjoyable and meaningful, and fostering a deeper understanding of the material. This serves as the foundation for a proposed action plan to integrate suggestopedia into literature teaching practices.

Keywords: *teaching literature, suggestion pedagogy, quasi-experimental, senior high school students*

Introduction

The study of literature is a vital component of language instruction, as it enhances students' fluency in their target language and exposes them to a variety of cultures, perspectives, and ideas. However, teaching literature effectively presents significant challenges due to its complex language, themes, and literary devices. Understanding these elements requires considerable effort and is essential for deep comprehension, which is a prerequisite for meaningful learning (David, 2010).

Despite its importance, literature is often undervalued and perceived as difficult. Students struggle with its intricate language, the need to grasp historical and cultural contexts, and the variability of interpretations. This difficulty is compounded by the extensive reading required and the disinterest many students show toward literary studies. In the Philippines, this disinterest is further exacerbated by colonial influences, which have led to a disconnect between students and their literary heritage (Bañez, 2016). Many Filipino students find literature's vocabulary too complex and irrelevant to everyday language (Hassan, 2018), making it seem inaccessible.

To address these challenges, educators need innovative teaching methods that make literature more engaging and relatable. Suggestopedia, an approach that integrates music, visuals, and interactive games, offers a promising solution. Music, in particular, has been shown to evoke emotions such as excitement, calmness, and inspiration, which can enhance cognitive abilities (Loque-loque, 2018). Given Filipinos' strong affinity for music, incorporating it into literature instruction could leverage this passion to improve student engagement and understanding.

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of suggestopedia in teaching literature to Grade 11 students at Zapatera National High School, Cebu City, during the 2022-2023 academic year. By comparing the academic performance of students taught using suggestopedia with those taught using traditional methods, this research seeks to provide evidence for the benefits of suggestopedia in fostering a more enjoyable and meaningful learning experience. Ultimately, this study aims to motivate students to develop a lifelong appreciation for literature and enhance their language learning.

Research Questions

This study determined the effectiveness of suggestion pedagogy (suggestopedia) in teaching literature among Grade 11 Senior High School (SHS) students of Zapatera National High School, Cebu City, SY 2022-2023. The findings served as the basis of a proposed action plan. It answered the following questions:

1. What are the pretest performances of the control and experimental groups?
2. What are the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest performances of the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there a significant difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the control and experimental groups?

Literature Review

One of the strategies that promotes English language and literature learning is the suggestion pedagogy or suggestopedia. In the 1970s, a medical doctor, psychotherapist, and educator from Bulgaria named Georgi Lozanov made a new approach called Suggestopedia. Lozanov worked with patients using his unique psych correction method. Suggestopedia is the study of releasing the human personality's mental reserves (the principle of joy and relaxation, suggestive interactions).

Consequently, (Larsen & Anderson, 2011) explained that there are numerous educators across various disciplines have dedicated considerable efforts to discover teaching methodologies tailored to student needs, with some innovating their own approaches aligned with prevailing educational standards. They then claimed that suggestopedia, a method targeting the subconscious mind, aims to assist

students in overcoming potential psychological obstacles that may hinder learning, effectively priming them for a productive classroom experience.

Moreover, Caskey, O. L., & Flake, M. H. (1976) comprehensively claimed and discussed suggestopedia or Suggestology which involves studying how suggestion impacts psychology, and Suggestopedia applies relaxation and suggestion techniques to learning. Developed by Dr. Georgi Lozanov, the approach, known as the Lozanov Method, aims to enhance learning efficiency. It incorporates mental and physical relaxation, deep breathing, positive suggestions, and background music to expedite learning or reduce learning time. The Suggestopedic approach theorizes that information bypasses emotional barriers and goes directly into long-term memory, resulting in faster and more enjoyable learning with higher retention rates for learners of all ages. Additionally, learners' self-concept improves due to increased achievement and positive suggestions inherent in the approach

Furthermore, Hertsovska, N. (2022) also claimed that the beneficial outcomes attributed to the implementation of the suggestopedia approach encompass several key aspects: learner-centered instruction, the alleviation of anxiety and the promotion of comfort among students, the provision of positive suggestions and the discouragement of negative ones by teachers, and the enhancement of students' self-confidence. Ultimately, suggestopedic teaching strategies aim to cultivate learning environments characterized by comfort, thereby bolstering learners' resilience, readiness, and relaxation while instilling hope and confidence in their abilities. This approach also aims to facilitate learners in surmounting learning obstacles and converting input into meaningful understanding. Additionally, suggestopedic instruction entails exposure to both situational exercises and authentic language systems, which is anticipated to notably enhance listening comprehension and the capacity for everyday communication in a foreign language.

In addition, Altun, M. (2023) also asserted in his review about the benefits of integrating Suggestopedia into language learning that suggestopedia operates under the premise that optimal learning occurs in a relaxed and comfortable atmosphere, often enhanced by music. It employs various methods such as music, drama, and visualization to create an immersive and stimulating learning environment for learners. Through the power of suggestion, Suggestopedia aims to eliminate negative emotions that impede learning progress. Utilizing positive affirmations and suggestions not only fosters self-confidence but also reinforces learners' belief in their capacity to learn, a crucial determinant of success.

There are many factors to consider when providing suggestopedic instruction, one of which is the method of correction, which should be indirect so that students do not feel ashamed of their mistakes. Another example is the instructional process, which is separated into three phases: The Preparatory Phase, The Concert Phase, and the Practice Phase. The first is known as the preparatory phase, in which the teacher presents a new subject and its concept and connects it to what has already been learned. The second of which is suggestopedic where sentences can be altered or repeated. The second phase is the actual suggestopedic session, which is referred to as the succeeding phase. It is divided between an active and passive phase known as "concert." The music in the active section is livelier than the music in the second section. During this stage, the students have their textbooks open, and the text is always displayed in both languages, with the foreign language version on the left and the native language version on the right. Following the introduction of musical beats, the teacher reads the entire text aloud and with appropriate pauses in such a way that the student's voice is rhythmically coordinated with the music (Schiffler, 1992).

It was also noticed that during the second half of the concert, which is the passive concert, the students put away their books and sat in a comfortable and relaxed stance. A soothing piece of music is played at this period, and the teacher reads the text with natural intonation. After the presentation, the music gradually fades away (Schiffler, 1992). After the teacher has read the text, it is repeated in the review phase which is the third phase of suggestopedia which is known as the Practice Phase. This section also includes question and answer sessions. Furthermore, creative transformations, games, and conversations or role playing are devised and will be presented dramatically by the students.

Moreover, according to Wang, S.L. (2023) which she comprehensively explained the suggestopedia method and its four key steps which are: Presentation, Concert, Elaboration, and Practice. She then asserted that these steps cater to different types of learners: those who learn by doing, seeing, and hearing. This highlights suggestopedia as a suitable choice for teaching English to speakers of other languages regardless of various types of learners in the teaching learning process.

The suggestopedia method includes six main aspects crucial for teaching and learning with this approach. As identified by Nosrati et. al. (2013), these aspects are: 1. Creating a comfortable setting for learning, 2. Using music in teaching, 3. Applying peripheral learning methods, 4. Encouraging error-free learning, 5. Keeping homework to a minimum, and 6. Incorporating music, drama, and art into lessons. These activities aim to make learning enjoyable and easy for students. It's believed that suggestopedia can speed up learning three times faster than traditional methods. The method follows four stages: presentation, concert sessions (active and passive), elaboration, and practice where students show what they've learned.

On this occasion, when instructing literature, educators utilize various teaching methods to witness students effectively retain and apply newfound knowledge. Consequently, it becomes imperative for teachers to establish an enjoyable learning atmosphere to foster positive educational encounters (Ompad, 2014). The researcher firmly believes that Suggestopedia holds promise as a valuable tool in literature instruction, leveraging elements such as music, art, a relaxed setting, and an encouraging instructor with a positive demeanor.

On the other hand, Bakhromova and Ergashev (2022) also revealed that the suggestopedia approach notably boosts students' overall

performance. This suggests that employing the suggestopedia method could prove highly effective in teaching vocabulary to both elementary and secondary school students. As such, educators may find it beneficial to incorporate suggestopedia techniques into their teaching strategies.

In addition, Kusner (2007) asserts that Suggestopedia is a fun and creative alternative to approaches that are more rigid, traditional, and artificial. Also, it gives a lot of useful and creative ideas to be used in the classroom, as well as a lot of ways to make the process of remembering things better. Also, suggestopedia can help improve students' behavior and attitudes, as well as their grades, the atmosphere at school, their attendance, and the morale of their teachers. Kusner also added that the first job of a suggestopedic teacher is to make the environment comfortable and calm before presenting the educational material. The teacher can do this by keeping his cool, having a positive outlook, and saying positive things.

Consequently, according to Sunardi, Waluyo, Suudi, and Wardani (2018), utilizing a suggestopedia teaching approach based on authentic themes. Themes that are derived from students' real-life experiences proved highly suitable for their conditions, needs, interests, and skills. This method fostered more engaging and meaningful learning experiences, ultimately inspiring students to actively enhance their skills within this enriched educational environment.

Moreover, according to Zaid (2014), improved learning occurs when students are calm, comfortable, confident, and intrinsically driven, with no negative feelings such as tension, worry, fear, or boredom. Furthermore, it was then given an emphasis that suggestopedia reinforces the efficiency and depth of learning, and the more enjoyable and rewarding an experience is, the more deeply it will be remembered. Providing students with a relaxed yet interesting lesson is therefore an essential aspect that must be taken into account.

In addition, Du (2009) explained that delivering a pleasant, energetic, amiable, and serene classroom atmosphere in a suggestopedic approach can help students overcome their psychological barrier and lower their anxiety. Du emphasized that teachers upon employing suggestopedia must also let their students make a few mistakes. This relieves stress and builds the students' self-confidence. Further, teachers must foster students' interest as interest is the best teacher. In relation to this, the teacher should come up with more various ways to teach, use vivid and entertaining language to teach students, and create a relaxing and light environment.

As suggestopedia was greatly given emphasis that it promotes harmonious classroom environment, Schoepp also reported in 2001 that songs can break up the routine of the classroom and that using songs to learn English creates a safe environment that can help students improve their four language skills. Several authors also say that they think songs can be fun and help students learn language skills. Because of this, it's clear that the fun part of learning a language through songs is directly linked to affective factors. So, it is important to teach senior high school students using Suggestopedia as a teaching tool.

Another literature underscores the utilization of suggestopedia within teaching and learning contexts, advocating for relaxation through music listening and extensive notetaking based on auditory input. This method is recognized as an efficacious approach for enhancing English retention and comprehension within speaking classes (Richards & Rogers, 2001). By emphasizing relaxation and active engagement with auditory stimuli, suggestopedia facilitates the internalization, understanding, and analyzing of the literary piece that has been read.

Moreover, the integration of music and note-taking aligns with suggestopedia's principles, promoting a conducive learning environment conducive to language acquisition and retention. This approach is supported by several authors, suggesting its effectiveness in language pedagogy. The use of song and musical material to execute the principles of suggestopedia (which contribute to the production of "joy and tension") promotes a strong emotional mood in learners, pleasure, and relieves weariness during classes.

On the other hand, Albert (2016) also suggests that teachers incorporate songs in classrooms for various reasons, with one significant purpose being the creation of a positive atmosphere conducive to learner motivation. According to her, songs play a didactic role in teaching, with even instrumental music fostering a relaxed environment that aids learning. Additionally, singing is enjoyable for most students and serves as a refreshing break from routine language learning activities. Music's ability to evoke deep emotional responses makes it valuable in different domains, such as enhancing emotional experiences in storytelling, as observed in literature (Brown & Volgsten, 2006).

Conclusively, music is often perceived as a potent influencer of emotions, motivation, and conduct across diverse contexts (Brown & Volgsten, 2006). Whether classical, contemporary, or folk, various genres of music offer viable options for educators seeking to integrate music into teaching practices. Notably, songs serve as effective tools for vocabulary acquisition, stimulating interest and curiosity among learners (Kocaman, 2016). By leveraging music's emotive power and intrinsic appeal, educators can cultivate engaging learning environments conducive to language learning and word retention.

The literatures reviewed and presented in this study have offered invaluable insights into the efficacy of suggestopedia in teaching literature. Through the integration of the principles of suggestopedia, educators can then enhance the teaching of literature, fostering deeper engagement and comprehension among students. Thus, the synthesis of these literatures underscores the importance and relevance of employing suggestopedia as an effective tool in literature instruction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a Quasi-Experimental Research Design (QERD) incorporating pretest and posttest assessments to evaluate the impact of Suggestion Pedagogy (Suggestopedia) in Teaching Literature of Grade 11 students. Quasi-experiments, which assess treatments without using randomization, help establish causal relationships between interventions and outcomes (Balaaldia, 2022; Balala, 2016).

In this research, two groups were analyzed: an experimental group and a control group. Both groups completed a pretest before the experiment started. Afterward, posttest results were compared to measure the learning gains of each group. The control group experienced traditional teaching methods, such as chalk-and-talk, while the experimental group used the Suggestion Pedagogy (Suggestopedia). Data from the pretests and posttests of both groups were compiled, explained, tabulated, and analyzed to address the research questions.

Respondents

The study focused on 60 Grade 11 students from the General Academic Strand (GAS) of the academic track. These students were divided into two groups: 30 students from section Hemingway, serving as the experimental group, and 30 students from section Shakespeare, serving as the control group. Both groups were matched based on age and final grades in their Oral Communication (English 1) class to ensure comparability.

The control group consisted of 16 female and 14 male students, while the experimental group included 17 female and 13 male students. The average age of participants in both groups was 17.75, and the average final grade in Oral Communication was 83.35.

Instruments

This study employed a researcher-designed pretest and posttest questionnaire to evaluate the performance of students in both the control and experimental groups. The material for the pretest and posttest was based on guide questions from "The Hinilawod" by Felipe Landa Jocano. For both groups, "The Summer Solstice" by Nick Joaquin was used, with the control group receiving traditional instruction and the experimental group experiencing suggestion pedagogy as an intervention. A posttest was administered to both groups following the intervention.

The four-item, criterion-based instrument used for the pretest and posttest underwent content validation by experts to ensure its validity and reliability. After validation, data was collected from the respondents. The collected data were then retrieved, recorded, tabulated, and analyzed. The study emphasized the comparison between traditional teaching methods and suggestion pedagogy in teaching literature to both groups.

Procedure

The researcher considered the following steps to ensure the success of the implementation and conduct of the study:

After the validity and reliability of the instruments were ensured, the researcher sought approval from the University of Cebu - Office of the Dean of Graduate Studies. After that, the approval to conduct was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent's office, where the school belongs, down to the Office of the Principal of Zapatera National High School (ZNHS). The researcher also asked permission and cooperation from the advisers of the selected respondents. After receiving approval, the researcher divided the research participants into two comparable groups: the control group and the experimental group. The same pretest was given to both groups, but in different classrooms. The research subjects were applied with literature instructions differently a few days following the pretest using two methods: the traditional approach and suggestion pedagogy (suggestopedia). The control group was taught via lecture, whereas the experimental group was taught via suggestopedia. It is also important to note that classes and discussions were held in a different learning environment.

Below is a semi-detailed description of how the teacher-researcher employed the Suggestion pedagogy to facilitate the teaching-learning process among the experimental group. It is essential to note that Suggestopedia utilizes a carefully structured methodology with four main stages: presentation, first concert, second concert, and practice.

In the presentation (preparatory phase), the teacher-researcher helped the students unwind and adopt a positive attitude, with the expectation that learning was going to be enjoyable and easy. Before starting the class, the teacher arranged the classroom so that students can move freely and feel comfortable, thereby creating a relaxed environment. The teacher-researcher set the mood of the class by providing series of preliminary activities such as starting with an opening prayer, checking of attendance, and giving brain exercise that served as an energizer to the students. Also in this phase, the teacher-researcher asked introductory questions like: how are you feeling today? Are you excited for whatever surprise this day might give you? Are you ready to listen to another story in the Philippine Literature?

The teacher-researcher initiated the class with a motivational exercise, also serving as a review of the topic "The Elements of a Short

Story" through a CLASSROOM BINGO activity. Each student was provided with a bingo card containing terms related to the elements of a short story. Via oral recitation, students responded to questions prepared by the teacher regarding the definitions of these story elements. As terms were correctly answered, students marked them on their bingo sheets. The student who achieved a sequence of 5 numbers or terms in a row, whether vertically, horizontally, or diagonally, emerged as the winner of the bingo game.

The teacher then introduced another game which was called "Pass the Aqua flask". The teacher placed a medium-sized box on the teacher's table, containing items and illustrations likely related to prominent women in the Philippines. The teacher then informed the students that a lively piece of music would be played as they passed the aqua flask among themselves. The person holding the aqua flask when the music stopped would choose an object from the box and describe it. This process extended to pictures, with students providing comments about each one. The cycle continued until all objects or pictures were selected.

Following the previous activity, the teacher spontaneously asked students to share their thoughts on the presented pictures. The teacher encouraged responses from the class, aiming for answers related to the characteristics of different renowned Filipinas. Subsequently, the teacher grouped the students into five (5) groups, each consisting of six members.

The teacher-researcher then started the lesson by instructing first on vocabulary. For this part, the teacher provided rolled papers with jumbled letters written on them. Students collaborated within their teams, attempting to unscramble the letters swiftly and identify the correct words (with only a few seconds allotted per word). Each group received 10 rolled papers, instructing them with forming ten accurate words. Once a group believed they had the correct answer, they recorded it on a small whiteboard. This process continued until the final word was added to the board.

The active (first) concert is the suggestopedic phase in which the material to be learned is to be presented. Nick Joaquin's short story *The Summer Solstice* served as the springboard for teaching literature. Such discussions utilized the concept of suggestopedia. During this phase, it is important to note that the teacher established a conducive atmosphere for students by playing a soothing piece of music through a laptop and speaker. The initial part involved a dramatic reading of the story, first by the teacher and subsequently by the students. The teacher began by reading specific lines aloud, emphasizing the vocabulary displayed on the board, incorporating well-placed pauses to synchronize with the rhythmic music, creating a somewhat dramatic effect in their voice.

Simultaneously, the students referred to their notes, highlighting the vocabulary within the given context. Notably, the teacher utilized visual aids, pointing at pictures, or engaging in actions relevant to the text. Following this, students were encouraged to stand and read the text aloud, accompanied by gestures or movements, allowing them the freedom to express themselves. The teacher provided both praise and minimal corrections for mispronunciations after the activity.

In the passive (second) concert phase, students were encouraged to unwind, set aside their notes, and assume a comfortable and relaxed seated position. They were instructed to listen to music while the text was quietly read in the background. Throughout this period, a serene musical piece played, complementing the teacher's reading of the text with natural intonation. The chosen music was specifically emphasized to guide students into an optimal mental state, facilitating the seamless absorption of the material. Following this presentation, the music gradually faded away. In this stage, the story analysis took place, involving active discussions between the teacher-researcher and the learners. Within the same groups, the teacher introduced another activity called "Pass the ball." In this game, each group tossed the ball to other groups, and if a member dropped the ball, they had to answer questions related to the discussion of short story elements based on the presented material. Notably, the teacher revealed the correct answers only after the learners responded to the questions about identifying the story elements.

An engaging and interactive discussion was anticipated, as the teacher-researcher encouraged students to share their ideas and elicited correct responses, meanings, or interpretations. Sufficient time was given for students to contemplate the story analysis. Consequently, teacher feedback was provided in a less direct and friendly manner, guiding and facilitating the teaching-learning process.

The final stage is practice, where the teacher employed various games like hot seat, jenga building, and sine mo 'to to reinforce and review the learning. Tools such as a whiteboard, timer, and jenga golden blocks were utilized for these activities. Question and answer sessions required active student participation. Additionally, the teacher-researcher selected a few students to summarize or review the material through interactive games, prompting active involvement. Students were encouraged to share their thoughts, and the teacher provided positive and friendly feedback. A mini conversation with a short act and the use of Readers Theater were employed to encourage students to share what they had learned, particularly in the sine mo 'to activity. Each group was assigned a specific part of the plot from the story "Summer Solstice." They created mini plays with their own written scripts, portraying different aspects of the plot. The goal was to represent the story's plot through continuous mini plays, serving as a check for students' comprehension.

While the experimental group received intervention through suggestopedia, the control group adhered to a more rigid or traditional teaching method. After receiving instruction in literature through two distinct teaching approaches, participants from the control group and experimental group appeared to be more prepared for an assessment. A few days following the introduction of new materials, the teacher-researcher conducted a posttest for both groups. It's noteworthy that the test was administered in separate classrooms for the study subjects.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions. The data was analyzed using the following statistical tools:

Frequency Count and Per Cent were used to summarize, analyze, and interpret the pretest and posttest scores/performances of the control and experimental groups. The t-test for two independent samples was used to determine the significance of the difference in the pretest performances of the control and experimental. Likewise, this test was used to determine the significance of the difference of the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups. The t-test for correlated samples was used to determine the significance of the difference of the pretest and posttest performances of the control group. Similarly, this test was used to determine the significance of the pretest and posttest performances of the experimental group.

Pretest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 1 presents the pretest performances of the control and experimental groups as evaluated by the three experts using the rubrics.

Table 1. Pretest Performances of the Control Group and Experimental Groups

Score Ranges	Description	Control Group		Experimental Group	
		Frequency (N=30)	Per Cent (%)	Frequency (N=30)	Per Cent (%)
61 - 80	Very Good	0	0	1	3.33
41 - 60	Good	11	36.67	7	23.33
21 - 40	Fair	19	63.33	19	63.33
5 - 20	Poor	0	0	3	10.00

Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 2 presents the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups as evaluated by the three experts using the rubrics.

Table 2. Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Score Ranges	Description	Control Group		Experimental Group	
		Frequency (N=30)	Per Cent (%)	Frequency (N=30)	Per Cent (%)
61 - 80	Very Good	4	13.33	8	26.67
41 - 60	Good	17	56.67	22	73.33
21 - 40	Fair	9	30	0	0
5 - 20	Poor	0	0	0	0

Difference of the Pretest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 3 presents the difference between the pretest performances of the control and experimental groups of the Grade 11 students.

Table 3. Difference of the Pretest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Variables	df	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
• Organization	58	2.489	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Content & Writing Style	58	1.782	2.002	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Voice	58	1.194	2.002	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Language	58	0.943	2.002	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Mechanics, Grammar & Spelling	58	1.349	2.002	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
• Overall Score	58	1.581	2.002	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Difference of the Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 4 shows the difference between the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups when lecture and suggestopedia are used in separate groups.

Table 4. Difference of the Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Variables	df	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
• Organization	58	3.880	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Content & Writing Style	58	3.907	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Voice	58	3.522	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Language	58	3.657	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Mechanics, Grammar & Spelling	58	3.691	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant
• Overall Score	58	3.840	2.002	Reject Ho	Significant

Difference of the Pretest and Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 5 presents the significant difference between the pretest and posttest performances of the control and experimental groups.

Table 5. *Difference of the Pretest and Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups*

Variables	df	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Control Group					
• Organization	29	3.167	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Content & Writing Style	29	4.223	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Voice	29	6.866	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Language	29	4.877	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Mechanics, Grammar & Spelling	29	3.474	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Overall Score	29	4.672	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
Experimental Group					
• Organization	29	12.961	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Content & Writing Style	29	13.793	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Voice	29	12.732	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Language	29	14.037	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Mechanics, Grammar & Spelling	29	13.853	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant
• Overall Score	29	14.247	2.045	Reject Ho	Significant

Pretest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

The pretest performances of the Grade 11 students at Zapatera National High School, as shown in Table 1, reveal the baseline abilities of the control and experimental groups before the implementation of suggestopedia. In the control group, 63.33% of students displayed fair performance, while 36.67% achieved good performance. Similarly, in the experimental group, 63.33% performed fairly, 23.33% achieved good performance, 3.33% obtained very good performance, and 10.00% performed poorly. The poor performance in the experimental group can be attributed to the lack of preparatory exercises before the test. These results highlight the necessity for formal research to improve literature instruction methods.

Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 2 presents the posttest performances, indicating significant improvements in both groups. In the control group, 56.67% achieved good performance, while in the experimental group, a higher percentage of 73.33% reached the same level. Additionally, 26.67% of students in the experimental group attained very good performance. The number of students with fair performance decreased in both groups, with none in the experimental group falling into this category. No students in either group performed poorly in the posttest, demonstrating overall improvement.

Difference in Pretest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

As shown in Table 3, there is no significant difference in the pretest performances between the control and experimental groups across most categories: content and writing style, voice, language, mechanics, grammar, and spelling. However, a significant difference was found in the organization category, with the control group outperforming the experimental group in structuring their responses. This suggests a baseline familiarity with organizational skills among the students.

Difference in Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 4 reveals a significant difference in the posttest performances of the control and experimental groups across all criteria: organization, content and writing style, voice, language, mechanics, grammar, spelling, and overall performance. In the experimental group, 73.33% achieved good performance and 26.67% attained very good performance, with none scoring in the fair or poor categories. Conversely, in the control group, only 13.33% achieved very good performance, 56.67% attained good performance, and 30.00% obtained fair performance. This indicates that suggestopedia significantly enhances student performance compared to traditional lecture-based instruction.

Difference Between Pretest and Posttest Performances of the Control and Experimental Groups

Table 6 highlights a significant improvement in the control group's performance from pretest to posttest using the traditional method, with 56.67% achieving good performance in the posttest compared to 63.33% fair performance in the pretest. This confirms the traditional method's viability in literature instruction. Additionally, the experimental group showed substantial improvement, with 73.33% achieving good performance and 26.67% attaining very good performance in the posttest, compared to 63.33% fair performance in the pretest. These findings demonstrate the significant impact of suggestopedia on student performance.

In addition, the preceding results manifested that employing suggestion pedagogy and traditional method in literature instruction leads to a more effective teaching-learning experience. Statistical analysis illustrated a substantial difference between the two approaches when applied to comparable groups. Furthermore, it became apparent that incorporating music, art, drama, and various games resulted

in a significant enhancement in students' learning and overall performance.

Conclusions

Suggestopedia has proven to be a valuable instrument for teaching literature, effectively enhancing students' language skills, comprehension, and engagement with texts. Its success in promoting the analysis of short stories among senior high school students suggests broader potential applications in various educational settings and literary genres. Future studies could explore the long-term effects of Suggestopedia, its use in analyzing poetry, and its integration with other teaching methods to make literature lessons more engaging. Additionally, investigating its application in teaching grammar or other disciplines could provide further insights into its versatility and effectiveness. By expanding the use of Suggestopedia, educators can create a more dynamic and meaningful learning experience, fostering a deeper appreciation for literature and language.

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